

Improving Nursing Leadership and Management Skills in PHC, Riyadh

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Abstract

Leadership and management are necessary for all potential registered nurse (RN) leaders. Every nurse has some degree of management and leadership responsibility. The healthcare workforce, effective leadership, and decision-making are priority topics. Other topics include achieving clinical and operational excellence, which includes, but is not limited to, innovation, patient advocacy, quality, diversity, equity, and adapting to changes in hospital and interdepartmental policies and procedures. This is a pre- and post-study for leadership training aiming to equip all potential RN leaders with confidence and knowledge in leading the center for achieving sustainable success of the organization. Through interactive lectures and workshops, the objective of the study is to enhance knowledge regarding staff plan management, to develop administrative and management skills, to enhance knowledge regarding supply management and storage standards, to ensure compliance with infection control protocols, JCI and CBAHI standards, and to improve knowledge on preceptorship & training programs. From the pre-exam of the seven staff who participated in the nursing leadership and management program, the percentage ranges from 34% as the lowest score to 86% as the highest score. An increase in percentage that ranges from 91% to 98%, which is a significant improvement after conducting the team leadership and management skills lecture. Leadership training positively impacts all parameter scores of leadership and management skills related to nursing administration, supply and storage, infection control and safety, training and preceptorship, and National and International standards of JCI and CBAHI.

Introduction

Leaders can be found in every organization. According to Alilyyani et al., leadership is one of the vital aspects of the nursing profession. All nurses must possess an affinity to have leadership abilities, for all of them are considered to be leaders [1]. Within the nursing field, a nurse leader may be qualified for management or leadership positions. Although management and leadership are frequently used synonymously, they are two distinct ideas with many traits in common [2, 5]. The art of leadership involves setting goals and inspiring others to reach their utmost potential in order to accomplish tasks, initiatives, or objectives.

On the other hand, management is pertaining to roles that have a concentration on tasks in relation to planning, organizing, prioritizing, budgeting, staffing,

coordinating, and reporting [2, 8]. Conversely, nurse leaders use a broad perspective of how regular day-to-day activities affect the overarching objectives of the healthcare institution; they inspire their group to meet predetermined goals by clearly communicating expectations to them.

Nurses can take on various leadership roles in different organizational contexts for as long as they are able to attain the required leadership qualities to impart their influence on their other colleagues [3]. Among the vital leadership techniques that are crucial for planning and executing (management) abilities are motivating and coordinating the workforce. Leadership skills are aimed at mobilizing the organization's members, whereas management skills are concentrated on using organizational resources. [4].

More Information

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In an era of ongoing progress in the healthcare industry, nurse leaders are essential driving forces of change as well as improving patient outcomes and experiences, as well as establishing and maintaining healthy immersive practice environments for the staff, according to Brigstock et al. The necessity of training aspiring and emerging leaders in nursing is driven by several professional challenges.

The development of leadership skills is especially an aspect to focus on to support emerging nurse leaders (ENLs) as younger generations of nurses are now entering leadership positions in earlier stages of their careers than their progenitors. At the same time, proactive efforts are being made to reduce further attrition from the current workforce. [6]. Upon the continuous process of healthcare practice environments complexity is still moving forward along with the impending nurse leader retirements, it is more urgent now to develop the future of nurse leaders [7]. Thus, it is essential to have proficient nurse leaders in an intricate and dynamic healthcare system [8] and to reach a milestone to influence innovation and change [9]. Which is in line with Daghan and Topcu’s study emphasizing common skills of nurse leaders that are as follows: “to be visionary and innovative; to have high communication skills; to be able to lead change; to be dynamic, passionate, determined, and brave; as well as being able to create a common vision between nursing and the changing health system” [8].

In that manner, nurse leaders must possess strategic management expertise and a firm grasp of nursing practice implementation in order to support the nursing staff in providing a high quality, patient-centered, and cost-effective care in the light of the evolving healthcare system. [9, 12].

But in hindsight, nurse leaders are facing significant barriers starting with the reluctance to change, poor teamwork, lack of vision and commitment at the higher levels, loss of confidence, inadequate communication, interdisciplinary relationships, lack of preparation for leadership roles and role conflict [11], excessive pressure, job insecurity, and absence of problem-solving skills [14].

To provide a solution, in accordance with Lavoie-Tremblay et al., a health care program can be an aid to foster the capabilities of nurses, as it is effective in improving their competencies, well-being, and satisfaction in terms of work not only with the participating nurses but as well as their healthcare leaders [13]. Therefore, nurse leaders should be able to receive a leadership training that can provide supportive, empowering, and relational leadership skills [10].

Methods

Seven nursing leaders in different clinics of PHCs in Family & Community Medicine at Prince Sultan Military Medical City (PSMMC) have participated in the nursing leadership & management skills training. The five topics covered in the training are the pre-exam, which was used to assess the knowledge of participants before the lecture, and the post-exam, which was done after a day of lecture and training. Scores of the participant are recorded and tabulated using a numerical table and a line graph.

Results and Discussion

In the pre-exam of seven staff who participated in the nursing leadership and management program, the percentage ranges from 34% as the lowest score to 86% as the highest score, as seen in Table 1 below.

Table 1: Nursing Leadership & Management (Pre - Exam Percentage)

Staff Nurse (SN) Participant	Topics discussed					
	Administration	Supply & Storage	Infection Control & Safety	Training & Preceptorship	National & International Standard of JCI & CBAHI	TOTAL
SN Participant 1	50%	50%	38%	28%	50%	35%
SN Participant 2	100%	70%	75%	76%	90%	79%
SN Participant 3	100%	70%	69%	48%	60%	59%
SN Participant 4	100%	90%	81%	85%	80%	86%
SN Participant 5	42%	70%	38%	24%	70%	35%
SN Participant 6	100%	80%	75%	48%	80%	62%
SN Participant 7	50%	0%	44%	33%	40%	34%

Table 2: Nursing Leadership & Management (Post - Exam Percentage)

Staff Nurse (SN) Participant	Topics discussed					
	Administration	Supply & Storage	Infection Control & Safety	Training & Preceptorship	National & International Standard of JCI & CBAHI	TOTAL
SN Participant 1	100%	60%	94%	93%	90%	91%
SN Participant 2	100%	80%	88%	99%	100%	96%
SN Participant 3	100%	70%	100%	96%	90%	94%
SN Participant 4	100%	90%	100%	100%	90%	98%
SN Participant 5	100%	70%	81%	100%	80%	93%
SN Participant 6	100%	80%	88%	100%	90%	96%
SN Participant 7	100%	80%	100%	99%	90%	97%

Figure 1: Nursing Leadership & Management Training

An increase in percentage that ranges from 91% to 98%, which is a significant improvement after conducting the team leadership and management skills lecture, is shown in the figure above.

The knowledge and skills of the participants before and after the lecture are compared in the above figure.

Data Analysis and Interpretation

To highlight the effectiveness of the Nursing Leadership Management Training Program, the seven nursing participants were gauged with the use of a pre-test and a post-test, to which each Staff Nurse Participant gained a drastic change in terms of scores upon participating in the mentioned training. The following participants will be coded as SNP with their respective numbers.

The scores are based on the percentage in the following topics, which are: Administration, Supply & Storage, Infection Control & Safety, Training & Preceptorship, and Nation & International Standard of JCI & CBAHI.

During the pre-exams, the majority of the SNPs have gained perfect scores, with an exception for SNP1, SNP5, and SNP7 for they scored 50%, 42%, and 50% respectively, in the area of administration. While in the Supply & Storage aspect, the scores are ranked as

follows: SNP4: 90%, SNP6: 80%, SNP2, 3, & 5: 70%, and lastly, SNP7 with 0%. There are varying scores in the subject of Infection Control & Safety, except for SNP2 & 6 and SNP1 & 5 gaining the same score of 75% and 38% accordingly. With SNP4 garnering the highest score of 81%. The remaining scores are SNP3: 69% and SNP7: 44%. Training & Preceptorship entails the following ranking of percentages: SNP4: 85%, SNP2: 76%, SNP3 & 6: 48%, SNP7: 33% and SNP5: 38%, and lastly, the topic of National & International Standard of JCI & CBAHI having SNP2 as the highest score with 90%, followed with SNP4 & 6 with 80%, next is SNP5 with 70%, along with SNP6 garnering 60%, then SNP1 with 50%, and SNP7 with 40%.

Based upon their total percentages, SNP4 (86%) has a significantly higher score than the other participants, as SNP2 (79%) takes the next place, and SNP6 (62%) takes the third highest. The overall ranking of the remaining participants for the pre-exams are: SNP3 (59%), SNP1 & 5 (35%), and SNP7 (34%).

Moving onto the post-exam scores, there is a significant spike within the participants upon taking the mentioned training, exhibiting its immediate effects on their knowledge.

Overall, the SNPs have gained a perfect score in the Administration Scope. Followed by an improvement in the Supply & Storage area as well, which are placed in an ordinal manner as follows: SNP4: 90%, SNP2, 6, & 7: 80%, SNP3 & 5: 70%, and SNP1: 60%. In the Infection Control & Safety, SNP3, 4, & 7 have managed to get perfect scores, then proceeding to SNP1 with 94%, SNP2 & 6 with similar scores of 88%, and at last, SNP5 with 81%. For Training and Preceptorship, SNP4, 5, & 6 have perfected the part of the exam, while SNP2 & 7 have 99%, then with SNP3 scoring 96%, and SNP1 with 93%. For the last topic that is regarding the National & International Standard of JCI & CBAHI, SNP2 have managed to garner 100%, while others have similar scores such as SNP1, 3, 4, 6, & 7, and along with SNP5 having a 80% score.

Comparing to their old percentages, the improvements were immediate despite the premises of the post-exams. Their ranks are: SNP4 who is leading with 98%, SNP7 which had shown a huge bump in their results with 97%, then SNP2 with 96%, fourth is SNP2 & SNP6 with 96%, SNP3 with 94%, and 93%.

Conclusion

Leadership and management training positively impacts all the parameter scores of leadership and management skills related to nursing administration, supply and storage, infection control and safety, training and preceptorship, and National and International standards of JCI and CBAHI. It is a suggestion to provide other means than a sit through training lecture to be able to fully amplify the potential of the existing nursing administration to be in-line with the complex and dynamic healthcare system to improve further the varying areas in terms of nursing leadership.

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